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VET, Patience and the Wealth of Nations

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Abstract

Context: Behavioral economics describe how preferences, experience, and individual characteristics relate to learning and choices and therefore determine economic behavior. According to (economic) choice theories, patience is a key driving factor behind economic development as it affects economic behavior, as visible in health, crime, etc. Dohmen et al. set up the relationship between *patience* and economic developments. It becomes clear that patience is strongly correlated to parameters like years of schooling, innovation, risk preferences and GDP per capita. We are interested in a connection between patience and the investment in initial and continuing vocational education and training (VET) by the state and by enterprises in different European countries. Our thesis is that the more patient a society is, the more exists a willingness of firms and of the state to invest in apprenticeships.

Approach: We use a sample of European countries and correlate their values of patience (from the Global Preference Survey) with the public investment in vocational training, with the firm participation in vocational education and training and with the enterprise expenditures on CVT.

Findings: It is likely that there is a relationship between patience and the companies' participation in training. So, patience-oriented societies foster firm investment in education. We cannot prove a relationship between patience and the public investment in vocational training or patience and the companies' expenditures on CVT.

Conclusions: From an education theory perspective, we reinforce our result: Patience-oriented societies – and their companies – tend to place a strong emphasis on education as education is a means to promote social mobility and reduce inequality, as it provides individuals with the opportunity to improve their economic prospects and social status. Also, education is a means to promote innovation and economic growth, as it helps to develop the human capital needed to drive technological progress and improve productivity.

Keywords

vocational education and training, VET, patience, company engagement in VET, Europe

1 Context and research approach

In the discipline of *behavioral economics*, we find a construct named *patience*, referring to intertemporal choices (effects of a decision will take place in a different time than the decision

itself). We use this construct to examine a possible interrelation between patience and education with a special regard to vocational education and training.

Behavioral economics describe how preferences, experience, and individual characteristics relate to learning and choices – and therefore determine economic behavior. This influence of individual conditions on visible effects can be related to learning theories in educational science: In contrast to behaviorism, where learning is a matter of stimulus-response within a black box, and constructivism, which does not define any truth and relates to the own personal experience (see e.g., Neubert et al. 2001), in social-cognitive learning theory by Bandura (1977) decisions and their emergence are central. Social cognitive theory can be used when explaining, predicting, and influencing behavior.

According to (economic) choice theories, patience is a key driving factor behind economic development as it affects economic behavior, as visible in health, crime, etc. (e.g., Chabris et al., 2008; Sutter et al., 2013; Courtemanche et al., 2014). The research debate calls patience to be the ultimate reason for variations in living standards around the globe and emphasize the crucial role of the so-called “proximate determinants” of development, i.e., the accumulation of physical capital, human capital, and productivity (Dohmen et al., 2016). In other words, the more patient a society is, the higher accumulation of human capital and knowledge is probable. The stocks of these resources differ vastly across countries, as empirical evidence suggests. This observation leads to the research scope of explaining how differences in these stocks arise and how developments of corresponding determinants can be conceptualized (ibid.). Concepts of path dependency show how characteristics like culture, history, or geography determine economic development.

Dohmen et al. (2016) proved in a first systematic investigation the relationship between patience and economic development. They titled their research “Patience and the wealth of nations” referring to Adam Smith’s *Wealth of Nations* (2008¹) and signaling the importance of patience regarding consumption and savings². They correlate patience with parameters like the countries’ years of schooling, with R&D expenditures, innovation indices, risk preferences, and GDP per capita. It becomes clear that patience is strongly correlated to all these mentioned parameters (Dohmen, 2019).

Sunde et al. (2021) identify the links between patience and education as a research desiderate. Therefore, we verify if there is a connection between patience and the investment in initial and continuing vocational education and training (VET) by the state and by enterprises in different European countries. Referring to the above-mentioned research results of patience, our thesis is that the more patient a society (on the country level) is, the more exists a willingness of firms and of the state to invest in apprenticeships. There is research on the costs of initial and continuing VET and their distribution among companies, private individuals and the public sector (e.g., OECD, 2022; Dohmen & Cordes, 2019), but no relation to the construct of patience is existing so far.

2 Methods

We use a sample of European countries because the European Union (EU) is one economic world region with close economic and political interrelations. Especially regarding education, the vision of the European Education Area (to be achieved by 2025) is supposed to enrich the quality, inclusiveness and digital and green dimension of Member State education systems (European Commission, 2020). We use N=17 representing Austria, Czech Republic, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Lithuania, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal,

¹ First edit in 1776.

² “Savings” here relate to household savings as well as to gross (public) savings.

Romania, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, United Kingdom (due to different availability of data, some countries are not included in all correlations).

Our basic dataset is the Global Preference Survey (Falk et al., 2015; 2018; Briq Institute, 2018) for patience and control variables. So, in the data analysis, the independent variable is *patience*, the dependent variables are: 1) the public investment in vocational training (*PublicExpend*; IVET public expenditure as percentage of GDP; Eurostat, 2022a), 2) the firm involvement/engagement in vocational education and training (*TrainSupport*; percentage of enterprises providing any type of vocational training to their employees; Eurostat, 2022b) and 3) the company involvement in continuing vocational training (*ExpenCVT*; enterprise expenditure on CVT courses; Eurostat, 2022c). We choose these variables referring to Busemeyer & Iversen (2011) who use them to analyse youth unemployment, wage bargaining and labour market stratification. Thus, our hypotheses are:

H₀: There is no statistical correlation between *patience* and *TrainSupport*, *ExpenCVT* and *PublicExpend*.

H₁: There is a statistical correlation between *patience* and single variables.

Using SPSS, we correlate *patience* to *TrainSupport*, *ExpenCVT* and *PublicExpend*, using partial correlations in a further step to measure the strength of a relationship between patience and single variables, while controlling for the effect of the other variables. Running a regression for the described model shows that the model is statistically significant.

3 Findings

We expected to find a correlation between the patience and the willingness to invest in vocational education. As a first indicator, the regression model is significant ($r=0.842$ and $r\text{-squared}=0.679$ with a standard error of 0.29).

When correlating patience to *TrainSupport*, *ExpenCVT* and *PublicExpend*, we see that the Pearson's r is significant for *TrainSupport* (0.743 with a significance level of 0.01 (2-tailed), so the relationship is highly significant) and for *PublicExpend* (0.503 with a significance level of 0.05 (2-tailed), so the relationship is rather weak but significant). *ExpenCVT* is not statistically related to patience (Pearson's r is 0.219).

By adding partial correlations (*patience* and *TrainSupport* as well as *patience* and *PublicExpend*) we find out that the correlation of *patience* and *PublicExpend* is a spurious correlation ($r=0.281$), while the correlation of *patience* and *TrainSupport* remains significant ($r=0.725$). Figure 1 shows the scatter plot of the linear regression model: It is likely that there is a relationship between patience and the companies' engagement in training in the population as well as the sample.

Figure 1

Correlation of patience and companies' engagement in training. Own compilation

4 Discussion and limitations of the research

In social-cognitive learning theory, we construct when problem-solving and choose in the way that we have been shaped and socialized. This leads to individual preferences, and a set of preferences (like within a geographic region) leads to economic developments. Economic developments are responsible for people's income, employability, and therefore for their well-being. In this context, VET is also important and can contribute to a society's well-being. When merging VET and the idea of patience, we can see a positive correlation for patience and the companies' participation in vocational education and training.

What can we learn from the patience-excursus in VET? Patience-oriented societies foster firm investment in education. We reject the null hypothesis and confirm H_1 . From an education theory perspective, we can reinforce this result: There are several reasons why patience-oriented societies – and the companies within them – tend to place a strong emphasis on education. First, education is seen as a means to promote social mobility and reduce inequality, as it provides individuals with the opportunity to improve their economic prospects and social status. Second, education is viewed as a means to promote innovation and economic growth, as it helps to develop the human capital needed to drive technological progress and improve productivity.

For a critical evaluation of the results, we want to focus on the construct of patience. The idea of patience is to indicate in how far time preference relates to future-oriented behaviors, resulting for example in economic variables like income. Therefore, we take a closer look at how the data has been collected. For the determination of the patience value, respondents were asked whether they would prefer to receive 100 euros today or 154 euros in 12 months from now. Following this logic, respondents decided to receive payments now or later within four more questions according to these choice questions. We can see that the patience value is collected via a monetary assessment of the participants. This is a comprehensible approach but does not take into account the monetary stability (or individual's perception of the stability), so to gain precise (inflation-adjusted) patience values, we would have expected to have this factor included in the survey in a direct way.³ To address this challenge, we could add control

³ In the questionnaire, it reads: "Please assume there is no inflation"; still, this does not include explicitly the expected monetary stability.

variables for inflation and interest rates, but we assume it makes a difference within the questioning already.

There are limitations in the research design such as we use the *individual-level* patience measures and *collective-level* financial (investment; expenditure) measures. Furthermore, a small sample (N=17) leads to the question in how far our results are representative. Though, the data comes from valid and representative statistics/surveys and in this case, a small sample with a significant model is an indicator for an actual relationship between patience and the companies' engagement in training in the population as well. Nevertheless, our approach could be extended and used for a regression with more countries around the world as the Global Preference Survey is available for 76 countries. Also, private educational expenditures by educational level could be included in a model. Beyond a continuation of this research approach, we consider further research to be useful, e.g., regarding the question whether educational institutions can change patience. Dohmen (2019) argues that programs that are helping and supporting developing countries would work if they would foster patient behavior, e.g., if institutions create a certain and stable environment.

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